

Centre for Artificial Intelligence

Project thesis Bachelor Computer Science

**Merging LLM's with Classical NLP Methods
for Large Document Set Exploration:
A Hybrid Approach to Exploring Swiss Case
Law**

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Date	15.12.2025

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PROJECT THESIS

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Submitted on
December 13, 2025

Study program:
Computer Science, B.Sc.

Imprint

Project:

Title:

A Hybrid Approach to Exploring Swiss Case Law

Author:

Date:

Keywords:

Copyright:

Project Thesis

Merging LLM's with Classical NLP Methods for Large Document Set Exploration:

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December 13, 2025

LLM, NLP, large dataset, law, court rulings

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of large language models (LLMs) has created new opportunities for building intelligent legal information systems. However, the reliability of such systems depends critically on the quality of their retrieval components. This thesis investigates a retrieval pipeline designed for Swiss court rulings and evaluates three search strategies: keyword-based retrieval, embedding-based retrieval, and a combined embedding-graph approach. The empirical evaluation, consolidated in Appendix C, demonstrates that while keyword search achieves high precision, it suffers from limited recall due to the constraints of traditional keyword extraction methods. Embedding-based retrieval significantly improves performance, and integrating graph-based contextual relationships yields the strongest overall results.

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List of Abbreviations

Art.	Article
BGE	Leading rulings of the Swiss Federal Court (Bundesgerichtsentscheid)
FIZZ	Factual Inconsistency Detection by Zoom-in Summary and Zoom-out Document
LDA	Latent Dirichlet Allocation
LLM	Large Language Model
NLP	Natural Language Processing
RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
TF-IDF	Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

Since the commencement of systematic judicial publication, courts across all levels in Switzerland have issued over 448'000 published rulings.¹ Of these, approximately 190'000 originate from the Swiss Federal Supreme Court (*Bundesgericht*), with an estimated 20'000 recognized as leading decisions (*Leitentscheide*).

Although Switzerland follows a civil law system rather than a common law one, judicial jurisprudence nonetheless plays a fundamental role in legal practice and the application of statutory provisions. In particular, courts are frequently required to concretize abstract legal concepts and open-ended clauses intentionally left by the lawmakers for interpretation by the judiciary.²

As a result, legal practitioners are routinely required to consult the corpus of judicial decisions. Such research may involve identifying rulings that interpret a specific statutory provision, define or concretize a particular legal concept, or address a comparable set of facts. In practice, more recent decisions generally carry greater weight than older ones, and the hierarchical authority of the issuing court also matters: decisions of higher courts take precedence over those of lower courts, beginning with cantonal courts of first instance, followed by cantonal appellate courts, and culminating with the Swiss Federal Supreme Court.

Given the vast size of the corpus, legal research is often a challenging and time-consuming task. Although numerous tools for legal research already exist, most remain predominantly keyword-based and return unstructured lists of individual rulings. As a result, practitioners must still manually sift through the results, evaluate their temporal and material relevance, and extract and aggregate the information necessary for their specific legal inquiry. It would be therefore highly beneficial for legal practitioners to have direct access to concise, structured summaries of the relevant case law pertaining to specific legal provisions or topics. This could be achieved

¹For an overview of the Swiss judicial system, see Appendix A.

²For example, in the area of construction and spatial planning law, the legislator has never precisely defined the term "hobby-based animal keeping" (*hobymässige Tierhaltung*). In order to assess whether such activity is compatible with residential or agricultural zoning regulations, cantonal courts are tasked with determining the threshold at which hobby-based animal keeping ends and a commercial operation begins.

through a hybrid approach that combines natural language processing (NLP) techniques with the capabilities of large language models (LLMs).³

1.2 Thesis Structure

Chapter 4 provides an overview of the dataset and the preprocessing steps applied to prepare it for subsequent analysis. Chapter 2 reviews the current state of the art in the analysis of large datasets using natural language processing (NLP) techniques and large language models (LLMs). The design and implementation of the proposed system are detailed in Chapter 5, followed by the presentation and discussion of results in Chapter 6.

1.3 Use of generative AI

Parts of the textual preparation benefited from the use of generative AI, specifically OpenAI's GPT models. While the conceptual development, structure, and content of the analysis were produced by the author, GPT was employed as a stylistic aid to refine phrasing, improve clarity, and enhance the readability of selected sections. All revisions made through AI assistance were critically reviewed and validated by the author to ensure accuracy and alignment with the intended meaning.

³While large language models (LLMs) are, strictly speaking, part of the broader field of natural language processing (NLP), in this thesis the term NLP is used in a narrower sense to refer to "classical" approaches: methods based on rule-based systems, statistical models, and feature engineering. In contrast, LLMs here denotes deep learning architectures, particularly transformer-based models trained on vast text corpora, which learn language representations end-to-end without manual feature design. This distinction is made for clarity when discussing hybrid workflows that combine classical techniques with LLMs.

Chapter 2

State of the art

The computational analysis of large legal corpora has developed substantially over the past two decades, driven by advances in natural language processing (NLP) and, more recently, by the emergence of large language models (LLMs). Existing methodological approaches can broadly be grouped into: (1) classical NLP techniques, (2) statistical and machine-learning-based text analysis, and (3) transformer-based and LLM-driven methods. Each class of methods offers distinct advantages for tasks such as information extraction, classification, document similarity measurement, topic discovery,

2.1 Classical NLP Methods

2.1.1 Preprocessing and Normalization

Classical NLP establishes the foundational pipeline upon which more sophisticated analysis methods operate. Core preprocessing techniques include tokenization, lemmatization, stopword removal and sentence segmentation.¹

In the context of legal texts, domain-specific considerations often apply:

- Multilinguality (German, French, Italian) requires language-sensitive lemmatization and stopwords.
- Citation formats, such as references to the Swiss Federal Court rulings, may be extracted using regular expression-based heuristics.

2.1.2 Rule-Based and Linguistic Approaches

Rule-based NLP remains important for legal corpora because of the structured and formulaic nature of judicial texts. Methods include:

- Named Entity Recognition via pattern matching, targeting legal entities (rulings, articles of law).
- Document parsing for identifying structures, e.g., distinguishing the facts from the considerations.
- Keyword extraction

¹For more information related to this techniques, see [1], in particular chapter 2.2

2.1.3 Vector-Space Models

Bag-of-Words (BoW) and TF-IDF[2] representations are frequently used to represent judgments as high-dimensional numerical vectors. Such representations support downstream tasks such as:

- Document classification
- Similarity analysis

2.1.4 Topic modeling

Unsupervised topic models are widely used for exploratory analysis of large judicial corpora:

- Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) enables discovery of thematic structures across the corpus.
- Dynamic topic models may help capture temporal evolution in jurisprudence.

2.1.5 Other

Graph-based ranking algorithms, such as PageRank[3], also offer a viable unsupervised approach for extracting domain-specific terminology. Although PageRank itself operates on graph structures rather than textual content, its underlying idea has been adapted for NLP through models like TextRank, which construct graphs directly from the text and apply PageRank-style ranking to identify salient terms[4]. Existing implementations of TextRank have shown high precision in the legal domain.²

2.2 Transformer-Based Models and Large Language Models (LLMs)

2.2.1 Embeddings

Embeddings are vector representations of words, sentences, or documents that capture their semantic meaning. By mapping linguistic units into a continuous vector space, embeddings enable algorithms to perform mathematical operations on meaning. For example, measuring similarity between terms or retrieving conceptually related documents. They are widely used to support vector-based search systems and other semantic retrieval tasks.

2.2.2 Transformers

Transformers are a neural-network architecture designed to process sequences of text using self-attention mechanisms. Instead of reading text strictly left to right, transformers evaluate relationships between all words in a sequence simultaneously. This allows them to capture long-range dependencies, contextual meaning, and subtle linguistic patterns more effectively than earlier architectures such as recurrent or convolutional neural networks.

²As concluded in [5], section 5.

Transformer-based models[6] such as BERT, RoBERTa, and their derivatives provide contextualized token embeddings and can be fine-tuned for a wide range of NLP tasks, including:

- Sentence and paragraph classification
- Named Entity Recognition

Cross-lingual variants (e.g., multilingual BERT) are particularly useful in multilingual legal systems such as Switzerland, although they may require adaptation to domain-specific legal language.

2.2.3 LLM-Based Techniques

Large Language Models (LLMs) are transformer-based neural networks trained on vast text corpora to learn patterns of language, enabling them to generate and manipulate text with human-like fluency. By leveraging billions of parameters and large-scale pretraining, LLMs acquire broad linguistic, contextual, and conceptual knowledge that can be adapted to specific domains through fine-tuning or prompting. LLMs can assist with tasks such as summarizing rulings, identifying relevant legal issues, extracting structured information, or generating query expansions for improved retrieval.

State-of-the-art methods use general-purpose LLMs (GPT-style, LLaMA-style, or Mistral models) either as zero-shot learners or with task-specific prompting. These methods support:

- Zero-shot or few-shot classification, bypassing the need for extensive labeled datasets.
- Explainable analysis, as LLMs can generate structured rationales, argument maps, or summaries.

LLMs also facilitate complex tasks such as harmonizing multilingual rulings, generating normalized metadata, and identifying implicit legal issues. However, concerns remain regarding reproducibility, hallucination, and transparency of reasoning.

2.3 Used methods

Rule-based approaches were employed extensively, taking advantage of the structured nature of the dataset. Standard preprocessing steps, including lemmatization and stopword removal, were also applied.

In the initial phase of the thesis, keyword extraction was performed using TF-IDF. However, the resulting term rankings proved insufficient for capturing the core concepts of the documents. In contrast, the application of TextRank yielded substantially more meaningful keywords, although the method did not consistently produce optimal results.

Named entity recognition was also explored using BERT-based models. Because the available model had been trained on a German (non-Swiss) dataset, its performance

on the corpus remained unsatisfactory.³

³Although the approach is highly promising [7], optimal performance would require training or fine-tuning on a Swiss-specific dataset.

Chapter 3

Approach

3.1 Problem statement

To generate meaningful summaries of jurisprudence related to specific legal provisions or topics, it is first necessary to identify all relevant court rulings within the legal corpus. Classical natural language processing (NLP) and information retrieval techniques offer robust tools for this task, including document ranking algorithms such as Okapi BM25, categorization methods like Bag-of-Words or TF-IDF, and topic modeling approaches such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA).¹ These techniques enable keyword-based search, relevance ranking, and thematic clustering, which are essential for navigating large collections of legal texts. However, such methods often struggle with semantic nuance and contextual understanding, particularly in legal language where precise interpretation is critical.

In recent years, the emergence of large language models (LLMs) has had a transformative impact on the legal domain. Tasks in which LLMs excel, such as text generation, summarization, translation, and contextual understanding, are central to legal research and practice. Nevertheless, LLMs depend heavily on the information they are provided, for example through Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) systems, and their effectiveness is constrained by the completeness and quality of the retrieved input.

This gives rise to a key challenge: efficiently exploring and analyzing large volumes of legal text to ensure that relevant rulings are not only found but accurately understood and synthesized. Relying solely on either classical NLP techniques or LLMs is insufficient. Traditional methods lack semantic depth, while LLMs require well-curated input data. The specific problem addressed in this work lies in bridging this gap, developing a hybrid system that combines the retrieval strength of classical NLP with the interpretative and generative capabilities of LLMs to support more effective and scalable legal research.

¹Although Okapi BM25 originates in information retrieval rather than linguistics, it is widely applied in NLP for document ranking. Likewise, LDA is a statistical topic modeling technique that can be applied to any type of discrete data, not only text (e.g., image features), but is most commonly used in text analysis.

3.2 Objectives and scope

The primary objective of this thesis is to design and implement an intelligent legal search and summarization system tailored to the specific needs of legal practitioners. The system aims to overcome the limitations of existing keyword-based research tools by providing structured, interpretable, and context-aware access to case law. More specifically, the system will:

1. Enable advanced search and navigation of case law through a graph-based database that captures the semantic and structural relationships between entities such as court rulings, legal provisions, and abstract legal concepts.
2. Leverage large language models (LLMs) to interpret natural language queries from users and translate them into structured representations that can guide searches within the graph database.
3. Produce a high-level jurisprudential overview, synthesized by an LLM, that takes into account the temporal progression of decisions. This overview can then be returned directly to the user or used to generate a response within a broader LLM-based legal assistant.

This thesis focuses on Swiss jurisprudence, specifically on published leading decisions of the Swiss Federal Supreme Court. The envisioned technique should allow a user or agent to retrieve the relevant jurisprudence related to one or more law articles or to a certain keyword or legal concept.

A legal concept is an abstract or concrete notion that has a defined meaning within the legal domain and is used by courts, practitioners, and scholars to structure legal reasoning. Legal concepts can denote procedural institutions (e.g., *Aktenedition*, the obligation to produce documents), substantive rights (e.g., *Grundeigentum*, property ownership), tangible objects regulated by law (e.g., *Fahrnis*, movable goods; *Waffe*, weapon), or broader doctrinal categories (e.g., *Treu und Glauben*, good faith; *Verhältnismässigkeit*, proportionality). Being able to query jurisprudence by legal concepts enables researchers and practitioners to identify how the courts have applied and interpreted these notions across different cases, even when the exact wording in the legal text or ruling varies.

The following examples illustrate how specific legal queries can be paired with concise summaries of the jurisprudence of the Swiss Federal Supreme Court (BGE). Each answer is structured with a short explanation and a chronological timeline of landmark rulings, demonstrating the Court's evolving interpretation of key legal principles.

Example 1: Proportionality in Criminal Law

Query: Summarize the case law of the Swiss Federal Supreme Court (BGE) regarding proportionality in criminal law.

Answer: The Swiss Federal Supreme Court applies the principle of proportionality as a constitutional guarantee under Art. 5 para. 2 and Art. 36 para. 3 BV. It is central in sentencing and in assessing measures that restrict fundamental rights.

Timeline of key rulings:

- **BGE 102 Ia 279 (1976):** Established that proportionality must guide all criminal sanctions and administrative measures.
- **BGE 124 IV 44 (1998):** Clarified that sentences must reflect both the seriousness of the offense and the offender's personal circumstances.
- **BGE 134 IV 82 (2008):** Emphasized proportionality when applying preventive detention measures.
- **BGE 139 IV 62 (2013):** Confirmed that long custodial sentences must be carefully weighed against rehabilitation prospects.

Example 2: Freedom of Expression and Criminal Sanctions

Query: Summarize the case law of the Swiss Federal Supreme Court (BGE) on balancing freedom of expression and criminal restrictions.

Answer: Freedom of expression (Art. 16 BV) enjoys broad protection, but the Court accepts restrictions where necessary to protect public order or personal honor.

Timeline of key rulings:

- **BGE 119 Ia 178 (1993):** Recognized freedom of expression as essential to democracy, but upheld restrictions against insults when proportionate.
- **BGE 131 I 333 (2005):** Stressed that criminal sanctions against political speech must be interpreted narrowly.
- **BGE 138 I 97 (2012):** Clarified that restrictions on artistic and satirical expression require strict proportionality analysis.
- **BGE 144 I 281 (2018):** Balanced hate speech regulation with freedom of expression, confirming the necessity test under Art. 36 BV.

Example 3: Data Protection and Privacy in Criminal Procedure

Query: Summarize the jurisprudence of the Swiss Federal Supreme Court (BGE) on data protection and privacy in criminal proceedings.

Answer: The Court regards privacy (Art. 13 BV) and data protection as fundamental rights that require careful proportionality checks, especially in criminal investigations.

Timeline of key rulings:

- **BGE 120 Ia 147 (1994):** Wiretapping and surveillance measures require a clear legal basis and proportionality.
- **BGE 129 I 12 (2003):** Declared that blanket data retention without individualized suspicion violates proportionality.
- **BGE 137 I 31 (2011):** Clarified limits on DNA profiling, requiring strict proportionality for collection and storage.
- **BGE 146 IV 76 (2020):** Reiterated that digital surveillance must respect necessity and proportionality, with judicial oversight.

3.3 Technical scope

The project scope encompasses the following components:

- **Corpus Preparation and Entity Extraction:** Using classical NLP techniques, such as regular expressions, rule-based approaches and algorithms such as TextRank to identify and extract key legal entities (e.g., law articles, court names, legal concepts) from the corpus of decisions.
- **Graph Database Construction:** Modeling the extracted entities and their relationships in a graph database (e.g., Neo4j), allowing efficient traversal and exploration of legal precedents, legal provisions, and thematic connections.
- **Natural Language Interface via LLMs:** Employing an LLM to interpret user queries and convert them into structured searches. This allows users to input open-ended or conceptually rich questions without requiring precise legal citations.
- **User Interface or Integration Point:** While not the primary focus, the system will be capable of returning its outputs either directly to the user via a search interface or as part of a larger LLM-based system capable of generating legal responses in context.

While alternative techniques could also contribute to achieving the stated objective, the scope of this thesis will remain limited to the components described above. Potential enhancements, including the integration of such methods, are left as directions for future research and may be explored in subsequent theses. Possible future work includes:

- **Improved named entity extraction:** Improving quality of extracted legal terminology by training a custom model (e.g. a BERT model).
- **Integration of Additional NLP Methods:** Incorporating topic modeling approaches (e.g., LDA) or other statistical and machine learning methods to broaden

the analytical capabilities.

- **Leveraging graph data:** Implementation of community detection for uncovering underlying structures (e.g. Louvain or Leiden algorithms[8]).
- **Automated Summarization and Traceability:** Implementing summarization techniques, guided or generated by LLMs, that preserve the legal meaning of decisions. Each summary must be referenceable down to the phrase level to ensure transparency and legal accountability.²
- **Evaluation and Output Generation:** Developing a mechanism for evaluating the quality and fidelity of summaries and using them to produce a jurisprudential overview that reflects the temporal and hierarchical weight of the rulings.
- **Structured Summaries of Selected Rulings:** Generating structured summaries that condense the essential legal reasoning and outcomes while maintaining traceability to the original sources, an essential requirement in the legal domain.

3.4 Methodological Overview

The dataset employed in this study is described in detail in Chapter 4. For practical reasons, the scope of the present work is restricted to the decisions of the Swiss Federal Supreme Court. Nevertheless, the methodology and system design have been kept sufficiently general to allow for future extensions covering the entirety of Swiss case law (including rulings of other courts, such as Cantonal and other Federal courts).

The preprocessing stage involves cleaning and standardizing the dataset. Key information, such as the date of the decision, references to legal provisions, citations of other cases, and general legal terminology, is extracted and stored in a structured format within a graph database. Legal provisions and inter-case references can be reliably identified through rule-based methods, such as regular expressions, owing to their standardized textual patterns. Legal concepts, which are less formally defined, must be extracted with either classical NLP techniques or by using a language model.

The processed data and associated metadata are stored in a Neo4j graph database. The search functionality is exposed via API endpoints, enabling programmatic access and integration with other applications.

Subsequently, user queries are processed by an LLM to generate semantically relevant search terms. These terms are used to query the graph database, after which the results are sorted by importance and supplied to the LLM as contextual input. The LLM then generates a summary of the relevant case law, thereby providing the user with an accessible overview of the legal landscape.

²E.g. by applying the FIZZ framework (Factual Inconsistency Detection by Zoom-in Summary and Zoom-out Document)[9]

Chapter 4

Dataset

4.1 Swiss court rulings database

While in Switzerland there is no official entity tasked with the collection of all court rulings, the association `entscheidsuche.ch` was founded in 2017 in Landquart with the mission of providing open access to all Swiss court rulings. Its online platform publishes all new rulings on a daily basis.

Documents available on `entscheidsuche.ch` are publicly stored in HTML and PDF formats. Each ruling is accompanied by a metadata file in JSON format, which is also publicly accessible. All data can be freely accessed at <https://entscheidsuche.ch/docs> or over their API endpoints^[10].

The platform operates as a privately run public service. All data collected and published by the platform is freely available for use and further processing by anyone.

Since the scope of this work is limited to the court rulings of the Federal Supreme Court, only the data from the corresponding folders has been downloaded (https://entscheidsuche.ch/docs/CH_BGE/, https://entscheidsuche.ch/docs/CH_BGer/).

4.2 Rulings

The relevant data, consisting of the leading court rulings as well as all other rulings of the Federal Supreme Court¹, comprises over 200'000 court decisions.

Court rulings are typically structured in two main sections. The first section outlines the relevant facts of the case, referred to in German as the *Sachverhalt*. This part provides a detailed description of the circumstances and events that gave rise to the legal dispute, establishing the context in which the court must apply the law. The second section presents the legal considerations, known in German as the *Erwägungen*. Here, the court analyzes the applicable legal rules, interprets relevant statutes and case law, and explains the reasoning that underpins its decision.

In addition, all the leading rulings of the Swiss Federal Supreme Court usually include a headnote, called a *Regeste* in German. This headnote offers a concise summary of the court's legal reasoning and the essential points of law addressed in the decision. The *Regeste* serves as a quick reference for practitioners, allowing them

¹For more insights about the ruling of the Swiss Supreme Court, see Appendix B

to grasp the core legal conclusions without reading the full text of the ruling. Since headnotes are not usually included in non-leading rulings or rulings of other instances, the present thesis will not consider them.

FIGURE 4.1: Structure of a leading court ruling of the Swiss Federal Supreme Court

4.3 Cleaning of the dataset

The dataset contains over 200'000 rulings. Before it is possible to proceed with content extraction, the dataset needs to be cleaned in order to obtain uniform chunks of plain text. Cleaning ensures that the text is free from noise such as HTML tags, inconsistent formatting, and duplicate documents, which could interfere with downstream processing and analysis.

4.3.1 Removing Duplicates

The dataset contains many duplicates, recognizable by the suffix *_nodate* in the file name. Therefore, it is necessary to remove these duplicates to avoid redundancy in the analysis. This step is performed by the function `<remove_duplicates>` which scans the dataset for filenames containing the *_nodate* pattern and retains only one version of each ruling.

4.3.2 Removing HTML

The rulings were originally scraped in HTML format, which includes tags, scripts, and other non-textual elements. To extract meaningful textual content, the HTML must be removed. This is done using the function `<convert_to_markdown>`, which parses the HTML and retains only the visible text content. Removing HTML ensures that subsequent text processing steps operate on clean, readable text rather than markup code.

4.3.3 Remove formatting

Even after HTML removal, the text may contain inconsistent whitespace, line breaks, special characters, or other formatting artifacts introduced during scraping. The function `<clean_text>` standardizes the text by normalizing whitespace, removing unnecessary line breaks, and converting special characters to a uniform representation. This step ensures that the text is in a plain, uniform format suitable for automated analysis.

4.3.4 Splitting headnote, facts and considerations

Each ruling generally consists of multiple sections, including the headnote, the statement of facts, and the legal considerations. For precise content extraction, it is essential to separate these sections. The function `<extract_sections>` detects section boundaries based on common headings and splits each ruling into its constituent parts. This separation enables more accurate analysis, as key legal terms, topics, and references to statutory law or other rulings are typically found only in the headnotes or the legal considerations, rather than in the factual section. Nonetheless, the facts are retained, as they may prove valuable for future extensions of the project, such as implementing a vector-based search to identify rulings with similar factual contexts.

While the structure of leading cases (BGEs) is well-standardized, other court rulings may follow slightly different formats that must be taken into account.

4.4 Dataset Token Distribution

After processing the rulings, the sections on facts and considerations were segmented (chunked) based on their existing numbering. Each resulting chunk was stored in the database as an individual node. Figure 4.2 presents the token distribution across all node types. The vast majority of nodes contain fewer than 500 tokens. Each court ruling contains approx. 5-10 nodes for facts and considerations.

FIGURE 4.2: Token distribution per node

Figure 4.3 illustrates the total token count per ruling. Nearly all rulings contain fewer than 10,000 tokens.

The relatively moderate token counts observed across most rulings suggest that they fall well within the processing capabilities of current large language models and embedding architectures.

FIGURE 4.3: Token distribution per court ruling section

Chapter 5

Implementation

5.1 Overview

To achieve the objectives outlined in Chapter 2, a comprehensive system has been developed that implements a complete data processing and retrieval pipeline. The system comprises three main components and two databases:

- An ingest pipeline, that reads the scraped rulings, extract information (between other references to other rulings and references to articles) and stores the data in the databases as nodes and relationships. The ingest pipeline also embeds the nodes and stores the vectors for semantic retrieval.
- A backend which retrieves the data in the databases and feeds it to an LLM to generate a response to the user's query.
- A frontend that allows a user to send a query to the backend and display the results.
- A vector database (Qdrant)
- A graph database (neo4j)

FIGURE 5.1: Overview of the application

One of the primary challenges in the system's development was ensuring scalability. To address this, the pipeline was implemented to operate in discrete batches, with robust progress tracking to allow interruption and resumption without reprocessing completed data, thereby ensuring idempotency. Due to the considerable size of the dataset, multithreading has been leveraged to reduce processing time.

An initial approach involved storing the embedding vectors directly in Neo4j; however, this strategy proved inefficient as the dataset increased in size, leading to significant performance degradation and elevated storage costs. Consequently, the vectors were migrated to a dedicated vector database (Qdrant)¹, which provides optimized storage and retrieval for high-dimensional data and allows the system to scale efficiently.

5.2 Ingest pipeline

5.2.1 Overview

The pipeline begins by ingesting rulings from the Swiss Federal Supreme Court, which are provided in HTML format.² Given the potentially large volume of rulings, loading all data at once could create significant I/O bottlenecks and strain system memory. To mitigate this, the pipeline is designed to process the data in batches, loading a manageable subset of documents into memory at a time. This approach not only improves performance but also enables the pipeline to handle large datasets efficiently, while supporting features such as progress tracking, interruption, and resumption.

The ingest pipeline was designed with modularity as a core principle, leveraging a factory pattern through the implementation of a PipelineFactory. This design allows the system to dynamically construct pipelines based on the type of rulings being processed, selecting the appropriate classes for cleaning, extracting, and saving the data. By decoupling these components, the architecture ensures that each stage of the pipeline can be independently developed, tested, and replaced, enhancing both maintainability and extensibility.

In the current implementation, the pipeline has been configured for two specific categories of rulings from the Swiss Federal Supreme Court: the leading cases and other regular rulings. For each category, specialized classes handle the particularities of text preprocessing, metadata extraction, and storage, ensuring that the nuances of the different case types are correctly

FIGURE 5.2: Schema of the ingest pipeline

¹To migrate existing embeddings and generate all the missing ones, the flag `--transfer-embeddings` can be used in the pipeline.

²A dedicated Python script is responsible for scraping these rulings from the court's publicly accessible repository. The scraping itself is currently not yet integrated in the pipeline and must be done manually.

addressed. This modular approach prevents duplication of logic while allowing optimizations tailored to the characteristics of each ruling type.

Importantly, the system’s design is flexible and can accommodate future extensions. New pipelines can be added for other kinds of rulings, such as decisions from different judicial instances or administrative courts, simply by defining new classes for the relevant processing steps and registering them with the PipelineFactory. This strategy provides a scalable framework for managing a wide corpora of legal documents.

5.2.2 Text cleaning

The next stage performs text cleaning and normalization. This process removes HTML tags, special characters, and non-relevant formatting, producing a clean and structured text suitable for downstream NLP tasks. Language-specific preprocessing steps (e.g., tokenization and stopword removal) are also applied to ensure consistent data quality.

5.2.3 Information extraction

Once cleaned, the text is analyzed to extract key legal references and structural elements:

- References to laws (articles, paragraphs, etc.) and citations to other rulings are identified using regular expressions.
- Keywords are automatically extracted using a textrank algorithm[11].
- Each ruling is segmented into semantic chunks, typically corresponding to the Facts and Considerations sections of the judgment. This segmentation facilitates both targeted retrieval and contextual embeddings.

Each extracted chunk is then vectorized using a state-of-the-art embedding model (OpenAI’s text-embedding-3-small). These embeddings capture the semantic meaning of the text and enable similarity-based search.

5.2.4 Saving the data

The last step in the pipeline stores the nodes and relationships (entities and relationships are displayed in figure 5.3) in the graph database (Neo4j) and the embeddings in the vector database (Qdrant). A unique ID is generated to ensure consistency during retrieval.

5.3 Graph database

The graph database stores the rulings, their relationships (e.g., cites ruling, refers to, cites consideration), and references to laws. This structure allows traversal-based queries and graph analytics, such as the

FIGURE 5.3: Schema of the graph database

computation of PageRank to identify the relative importance of rulings based on citation networks.

The graph database schema, outlined in the image 5.3, models the relationships between Swiss Federal Supreme Court rulings, their structure (facts, considerations), and their connections to norms (laws and articles).

This representation enables complex reasoning over the legal corpus, such as tracing citation networks, identifying referenced legal bases, and exploring thematic connections between cases. For the implementation of the project an AuraDB instance of Neo4j has been used.

5.4 Vector database

The vector database is responsible for storing the embeddings of the text chunks generated from the rulings. By representing the text in a high-dimensional vector space, the system can perform efficient similarity searches, enabling retrieval of semantically related rulings even when exact keyword matches are absent. For this purpose, a Qdrant Cloud instance was used, providing scalability through clustering. In this implementation, all rulings, regardless of type or category, are stored within a single collection.

5.5 Search application

5.5.1 Overview

To enable users to query the databases and demonstrate different search strategies, a web-based application has been developed. The system consists of a backend, which performs the retrieval, and a frontend, which communicates with the backend via a WebSocket connection to support real-time interactions. Both components have been deployed to Azure Cloud using Docker and Kubernetes.

The results retrieved from the databases are passed to a large language model (LLM, OpenAI's GPT-4.1), which uses the retrieved nodes as context to generate a coherent, human-readable reply. This integration allows the system to provide answers that are not only relevant but also well-structured and easy for users to understand.

Backend

The backend is implemented using the FastAPI framework and leverages Langgraph to integrate multiple search strategies, as described in Chapter 5.5.2. This setup allows the backend to efficiently handle API requests, manage queries, and coordinate retrieval operations from both the graph and vector databases.

Frontend

The frontend is built on **Next.js** and provides a user-friendly interface for submitting queries and selecting the desired search mode.

FIGURE 5.4: Query section in the frontend

Query results are streamed to the right-hand panel in real time (Figure 5.4). In addition to displaying the generated answer, the frontend presents their source information, ranked according to PageRank values to indicate relative importance or relevance (Figure 5.5).

FIGURE 5.5: Sources displayed in the frontend

5.5.2 Search strategies

The system implements three types of search strategies, each designed to retrieve and contextualize relevant rulings from the database.

Of the three strategies, two (embeddings and embeddings with graph) support what is known as multi-hop question answering. In such settings, a single retrieval step is often insufficient to gather all information required for a complete answer. Consequently, the system must evaluate after each retrieval cycle whether the extracted evidence is adequate. If it is not, the model generates one or more sub-questions and iteratively repeats the retrieval–assessment process until enough information has been accumulated to produce a satisfactory answer. This search process is defined as multi hop question answering[12] [13].

Keywords

The first strategy, keyword-based search, generates search terms from the user query and extracts any relevant law articles if provided. If specific law articles are identified, the search is restricted to nodes associated with those articles; otherwise, a global search across all nodes is performed. The initially retrieved nodes are then

verified for relevance, and their neighboring nodes (i.e. consideration nodes coming before and after the retrieved node) are also retrieved to enrich the context. Based on this expanded context, the system generates an answer that reflects both the direct and related information.

FIGURE 5.6: Keyword search flow

This search strategy could potentially also implement graph traversal based on references to law articles and other court rulings, as done with the third search strategy, based on embeddings and graphs.

Embeddings

The second strategy is a vector-based search, which leverages embeddings to perform semantic retrieval. Based on the user's input, search queries are generated by prompting an LLM. The generated queries are then converted into vector representations, and the vector database is queried for the most similar chunks. The retrieved chunks are then verified for relevance by querying an LLM, and if necessary, the system performs additional searches. Subsequent queries (up to five iterations) are dynamically generated based on the nodes retrieved in the previous searches, enabling iterative refinement of results and improving recall.

FIGURE 5.7: Embedding search flow

Embeddings with graph

The third strategy extends the vector-based approach by incorporating neighbor references during the relevance-verification step. When an LLM assesses the relevance of a retrieved node, it simultaneously extracts references to other rulings contained within that node. If such references are found, the corresponding neighboring nodes are also retrieved and evaluated for relevance. This procedure, referred to as a neighbor visit, can be repeated up to ten iterations, effectively performing a graph traversal that explores connected nodes throughout the network. Through this traversal, the system constructs a richer and more interconnected context for answer generation, capturing both direct links and more distant relationships among rulings.

FIGURE 5.8: Embedding with graph search flow

5.6 Results

After the execution of the pipeline, the system reaches a structured and fully indexed state. All relevant information extracted from the rulings is stored in Neo4j, providing a graph-based representation that supports complex queries over the corpus. Simultaneously, the textual content of the rulings is embedded and stored in Qdrant, enabling efficient vector similarity search across all documents. This dual storage strategy ensures that the dataset is both structurally navigable through Neo4j and semantically searchable through the vector database, providing a robust foundation for subsequent analyses and retrieval tasks.

Through the user interface, users can query the data using multiple search strategies, by keywords, embeddings or embeddings with graph navigation.

Chapter 6

Results

6.1 Overview

To evaluate the retrieval performance and the effectiveness of the implemented search strategies, a set of ten test queries was compiled. These queries were derived from authoritative law books and scholarly publications. For each query, the respective source provides a list of cited court rulings, which serves as the reference set for evaluation. The complete overview of queries and corresponding rulings is presented in appendix C, table C.1. Although the queries are formulated in German, this has no impact on the evaluation, as the system is designed to operate in a multilingual context.

For each query, searches were conducted using all implemented search strategies. The retrieved results were then compared with the reference rulings cited in the source material. On this basis, true positives (TP, relevant rulings correctly retrieved) were identified, along with false positives (FP, non-relevant rulings retrieved by the system) and false negatives (FN, reference rulings that the system failed to retrieve). Using these values, the standard evaluation metrics precision, recall, and the F1 score were computed to assess retrieval accuracy and completeness across the different search strategies (appendix C, tables C.2, C.3, C.4).

An overview of the aggregated retrieval results is displayed in Table 6.1. The quality of the LLM-generated response has not been analyzed in this thesis and it's left for future works.

Search strategy	Average precision	Average recall	Average F1
Keyword	0.78	0.49	0.58
Embedding	0.81	0.74	0.76
Embedding + graph	0.86	0.85	0.84

TABLE 6.1: Test results - Averages

6.2 Retrieval performance

To compare the effectiveness of the different search strategies, the evaluation measured average precision, average recall, and the average F1 score across all test cases. These metrics provide a quantitative perspective on how well each method identifies and ranks relevant documents.

Table 6.1 summarizes the results:

- The keyword-based approach achieves relatively high precision (0.78) but demonstrates limited recall (0.49), indicating that it identifies relevant documents accurately but fails to capture a substantial portion of the relevant information in the corpus.
- The embedding-based approach performs more consistently, improving both precision (0.81) and recall (0.74) and achieving a markedly higher F1 score (0.76). This suggests that semantic retrieval yields broader, more balanced coverage.
- The combined embedding + graph approach produces the strongest results, achieving the highest precision (0.86), recall (0.85), and F1 score (0.84). This indicates that leveraging graph-based contextual relationships enhances retrieval robustness and relevance ranking.

Overall, the results show a clear performance improvement when moving from keyword search to embedding-based retrieval, and a further improvement when enriching embeddings with graph structure.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

7.1 Interpretation of results

The retrieval component performs reliably across the evaluated strategies, with the combined embedding and graph-based method delivering the best overall results.

The performance of the keyword-based search strategy is however strongly influenced by the quality of the underlying keyword extraction method. For the original objective, extracting all legally relevant terms from the documents, the applied approaches (TextRank and TF-IDF) proved insufficient.

Both methods are unsupervised and surface-level; they capture statistical or structural prominence but not the semantic and domain-specific nuances characteristic of Swiss legal terminology. A more advanced extraction pipeline, for example one based on a BERT model trained on Swiss legal data, could potentially achieve substantially higher extraction precision and recall¹.

With sufficiently high-quality keyword extraction, the resulting terms could be represented as nodes in the graph database. This would not only improve the classical keyword search but would also enable structural graph analysis, making it possible to identify conceptual relationships and explore legal knowledge patterns within the dataset.

7.2 Outlook

The results of this thesis highlight several promising directions for future work. One major avenue for improvement, as explained above, lies in the development of a domain-specific language model tailored to Swiss legal texts. A BERT model trained on a large corpus of Swiss federal and cantonal legal documents could capture domain-specific vocabulary and interpretive nuances far more effectively.

Another central direction for future work concerns the systematic evaluation of the responses generated by large language models. Although the present thesis focuses mainly on retrieval performance, the long-term goal would also be to build a robust evaluation framework capable of assessing the factual consistency of LLM-generated legal answers. Recent advancements in abstractive summarization research, particularly methods for identifying factual inconsistencies—provide a strong

¹As suggested by [7]

foundation for this. In particular, techniques such as FIZZ (Factual Inconsistency Detection by Zoom-in Summary and Zoom-out Document)[9] demonstrate how decomposing text into fine-grained atomic facts can offer interpretable and highly accurate inconsistency detection. Adapting such an approach to the legal domain would allow generated LLM responses to be evaluated against authoritative legal sources, ensuring that each individual factual unit is grounded in the retrieved documents.

A future evaluation system following this paradigm could decompose both the LLM's response and the retrieved legal context into atomic legal facts, align them at varying levels of granularity, and flag contradictions or unsupported claims. This would yield an assessment framework that is not only more precise but also transparent, enabling practitioners and researchers to trace incorrect outputs back to specific factual components. Ultimately, such a system could form the backbone of a reliable fact-checking layer for legal AI applications, ensuring that models produce outputs not merely fluent but verifiably correct.

In summary, training a Swiss-legal BERT model and implementing a fine-grained factual consistency evaluation system represent two major steps toward a fully reliable legal-AI pipeline. By combining domain-specific language understanding with interpretable factual validation, future work can significantly advance the quality, trustworthiness, and practical applicability of legal LLM systems.

Appendix A

Overview of the Swiss Court System

Switzerland has a federalist structure, and its judiciary is divided into cantonal and federal levels, each with multiple instances. The system ensures independence of the judiciary and guarantees the right to a fair trial.

A.1 Cantonal Court System

Each of the 26 cantons has its own court system, governed by cantonal laws. Despite minor structural differences, most cantons follow a similar three-instance system:

- *First Instance*: Typically, District Courts (Bezirksgerichte/Tribunaux d'arrondissement/Pretura) or Local Courts handle civil, criminal, and administrative matters at the initial level.
- *Second Instance*: Cantonal High Courts or Courts of Appeal (Kantonsgerichte/Tribunaux cantonaux/Tribunale cantonale) review decisions from lower courts upon appeal.
- *Specialized Courts*: Some cantons have specialized courts for labor, tenancy, or commercial matters.

A.2 Federal Court System

At the Federal level there are three courts.

- *Federal Supreme Court* (Bundesgericht/Tribunal fédéral/Tribunale federale): Located in Lausanne (and Lucerne for social security matters), it is the highest judicial authority in Switzerland. It primarily hears appeals on civil, criminal, administrative, and constitutional matters from cantonal courts or federal administrative courts.
- *Federal Criminal Court* (Bundesstrafgericht/Tribunal pénal fédéral): Based in Bellinzona, it handles serious federal crimes such as terrorism, organized crime, and money laundering.

- *Federal Administrative Court* (Bundesverwaltungsgericht/Tribunal administratif fédéral): Located in St. Gallen, it reviews decisions of federal administrative authorities.
- *Federal Patent Court* (Bundespatentgericht/Tribunal fédéral des brevets): This court has exclusive jurisdiction over patent disputes and is located in St. Gallen.

Appendix B

Publication Practice of the Federal Supreme Court

This appendix provides a brief overview of the publication practices of the Swiss Federal Supreme Court. For further details on its organization and additional sources, we refer to the Information Sheet on the Federal Supreme Court (*Merkblatt zum Bundesgericht*) published by the University of Zurich[14].

B.1 Numbering of the dossiers

All cases dealt with by the Federal Supreme Court are recorded and sorted, taking into account four identifiers (e.g. 4D_38/2007):

Number for the division:	4D_38/2007
Letter for the type of proceeding:	4D_38/2007
Consecutive number of the transaction dealt with:	4D_38/2007
Year:	4D_38/2007

Number of division

1	I. Public law division
2	II. Public law division
3	(reserve)
4	I. Civil law division
5	II. Civil law division
6	Criminal law division
7	(reserve)
8	I. Social law division
9	II. Social law division
11-14	Special dossiers

Types of proceedings

- A** Appeal in civil matters
- B** Appeal in criminal matters
- C** Appeal in public law matters
- D** Subsidiary constitutional appeal
- E** Action under Art. 120 BGG
- F** Revision
- G** Explanation and correction
- T** Notice of supervision
- U** Internal exchanges of views
- V** External exchanges of views
- W** ECHR consultation
- X,Y** Order and appeal under the APA
- Z** Voluntary jurisdiction

Consecutive numbering and year

The numbering is consecutive: Judgment 4D_38/2007 is therefore the 38th case of the First Civil Division in 2007. It concerned a constitutional complaint.

B.2 Leading cases

Since 1875, after a reorganization of the judicial system under the 1874 Federal Constitution, Switzerland has published its most important court rulings in an official report to ensure public access. Over the years, this collection has included only about 5% of all decisions, focusing on landmark cases and rulings that confirm or change existing case law, the ones that shape the future development of the legal system.

The collection was not originally organized, but over time it was gradually divided into sections (volumes):

Volumes before 1994

- Ia** Constitutional law
- Ib** Administrative and international public law
- II** Civil law
- III** Debt enforcement and bankruptcy law
- IV** Criminal law
- V** Social insurance law

Volumes after 1995

- I** Constitutional law
- II** Administrative and international public law
- III** Civil law and debt enforcement and bankruptcy law
- IV** Criminal law
- V** Social insurance law

The format for citing a decision published in the official collection of leading cases is as follows (for example, BGE 123 II 456)

- **BGE**: Bundesgerichtsentscheid (Federal supreme court).

- **123:** Year counted from the start of published case law (1875).
- **II:** Volume II, Administrative and international public law.
- **456:** Page 456 within the relevant volume

Appendix C

Testing results

ID	Query	Rulings cited in book	Source
1	Gem. Art. 6 GlG muss eine betroffene Person die Diskriminierung glaubhaft machen. Was bedeutet das? Wem trifft die Beweislast?	BGE 130 III 145 BGE 144 II 65	[15]
2	Was sind die Voraussetzungen für einen rechtmässige Arbeitskampf?	BGE 125 III 277 BGE 132 III 122	[15]
3	Im schweizerisches Zivilprozessrecht, wenn sind die Parteien zu Rechtsfragen anzuhören (entgegen dem Grundsatz "Iura novit curia")?	BGE 130 III 35 BGE 129 II 497 BGE 127 V 431 4A_178/2015	[16]
4	Wer trägt die Kosten für eine Scheidungsklage im Falle eines Rückzuges?	BGE 139 III 358	[16]
5	Im Rahmen der Verwertungserlös, gehören die Grundstückgewinnsteuern zu den Verwertungskosten?	5A 989/2016 5A 651/2015 5A 229/2009 BGE 122 III 246	[17]
6	Kann man eine Betreuung fortführen wenn das Rechtsvorschlag definitiv beseitigt worden ist aber der Schuldner weder eine Vorladung zu einer Rechtsöffnungsverhandlung noch den Rechtsöffnungsentscheid erhalten hat?	5A 738/2010 BGE 130 III 396	[17]
7	In Art. 231 StGB, wie muss man das Begriff "Verbreiten" interpretieren?	BGE 131 IV 1 BGE 125 IV 242 BGE 134 IV 193 BGE 116 IV 125	[18]
8	Gibt es eine Reduktion des Schadenersatzes wegen mitwirkenden Zufalls bei Kausalhaftungstatbeständen?	BGE 57 II 46 BGE 57 II 110 BGE 117 II 50	[19]
9	Welche Schranken der Eigentumsausübung ergeben sich as dem Nachbarrecht und öffentlich-rechtlichen Vorschriften?	BGE 107 II 134 BGE 91 II 183 BGE 88 II 331 BGE 82 II 397	[19]
10	Muss das bestehen einer Übung oder eines Ortsgebrauchs bewiesen werden?	BGE 94 II 159 BGE 91 II 358 BGE 90 II 100 BGE 86 II 257	[20]

TABLE C.1: Test queries

Query ID	TP	FP	FN	Precision	Recall	F1
1	9	0	1	1.00	0.90	0.95
2	3	0	2	1.00	0.60	0.75
3	3	4	4	0.43	0.43	0.43
4	3	0	1	1.00	0.75	0.86
5	1	0	4	1.00	0.20	0.33
6	2	0	1	1.00	0.67	0.80
7	1	1	3	0.50	0.25	0.33
8	2	3	3	0.40	0.40	0.40
9	4	0	4	1.00	0.50	0.67
10	1	1	4	0.50	0.20	0.29

TABLE C.2: Test results - keywords

Query ID	TP	FP	FN	Precision	Recall	F1
1	6	2	1	0.75	0.86	0.80
2	3	0	2	1.00	0.60	0.75
3	10	3	4	0.77	0.71	0.74
4	2	0	0	1.00	1.00	1.00
5	2	1	3	0.67	0.40	0.50
6	17	4	1	0.81	0.94	0.87
7	3	0	2	1.00	0.60	0.75
8	11	9	3	0.55	0.79	0.65
9	23	3	4	0.88	0.85	0.87
10	7	4	4	0.64	0.64	0.64

TABLE C.3: Test results - embeddings

Query ID	TP	FP	FN	Precision	Recall	F1
1	27	4	0	0.87	1.00	0.93
2	3	0	2	1.00	0.60	0.75
3	25	8	4	0.76	0.86	0.81
4	5	0	0	1.00	1.00	1.00
5	6	1	1	0.86	0.86	0.86
6	7	1	1	0.88	0.88	0.88
7	5	0	1	1.00	0.83	0.91
8	14	7	3	0.67	0.82	0.74
9	58	17	4	0.77	0.94	0.85
10	9	3	4	0.75	0.69	0.72

TABLE C.4: Test results - embeddings and graph

Bibliography

- [1] Christopher D. Manning, Prabhakar Raghavan, and Hinrich Schütze. *Introduction to Information Retrieval*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2008. ISBN: 978-0-521-86571-5. URL: <http://nlp.stanford.edu/IR-book/information-retrieval-book.html>.
- [2] Karen Sparck Jones. "A statistical interpretation of term specificity and its application in retrieval". In: *Document Retrieval Systems*. GBR: Taylor Graham Publishing, 1988, pp. 132–142. ISBN: 0947568212.
- [3] Lawrence Page et al. *The PageRank Citation Ranking: Bringing Order to the Web*. Tech. rep. Stanford Digital Library Technologies Project, 1998. URL: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/summary?doi=10.1.1.31.1768>.
- [4] Rada Mihalcea and Paul Tarau. "TextRank: Bringing Order into Text". In: *Proceedings of the 2004 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Ed. by Dekang Lin and Dekai Wu. Barcelona, Spain: Association for Computational Linguistics, July 2004, pp. 404–411. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/W04-3252/>.
- [5] Saransh Rajput et al. "N-Grams TextRank A Novel Domain Keyword Extraction Technique". In: *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Natural Language Processing (ICON): TermTraction 2020 Shared Task*. Ed. by Dipti Misra Sharma et al. Patna, India: NLP Association of India (NLP AI), Dec. 2020, pp. 9–12. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2020.icon-termtraction.3/>.
- [6] Jacob Devlin et al. *BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding*. 2019. arXiv: 1810.04805 [cs.CL]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805>.
- [7] Harshil Darji, Jelena Mitrović, and Michael Granitzer. "German BERT Model for Legal Named Entity Recognition". In: *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence*. SCITEPRESS - Science and Technology Publications, 2023, pp. 723–728. DOI: 10.5220/0011749400003393. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5220/0011749400003393>.
- [8] V. A. Traag, L. Waltman, and N. J. van Eck. "From Louvain to Leiden: guaranteeing well-connected communities". In: *Scientific Reports* 9.1 (Mar. 2019). ISSN: 2045-2322. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-019-41695-z. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-41695-z>.
- [9] Joonho Yang et al. "FIZZ: Factual Inconsistency Detection by Zoom-in Summary and Zoom-out Document". In: *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Ed. by Yaser Al-Onaizan, Mohit Bansal, and Yun-Nung Chen. Miami, Florida, USA: Association for Computational Linguistics, Nov. 2024, pp. 30–45. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2024.emnlp-main.3. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2024.emnlp-main.3/>.
- [10] entscheidensuche.ch. *Entscheidungsuche API description*. <https://entscheidensuche.ch/pdf/EntscheidungsucheAPI.pdf>. Accessed: 2025-08-19. 2022.

- [11] Paco Nathan. *PyTextRank, a Python implementation of TextRank for phrase extraction and summarization of text documents*. 2016. DOI: [10 . 5281 / zenodo . 4637885](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4637885). URL: <https://github.com/DerwenAI/pytextrank>.
- [12] Zhouyu Jiang et al. *Retrieve, Summarize, Plan: Advancing Multi-hop Question Answering with an Iterative Approach*. 2025. arXiv: [2407 . 13101](https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.13101) [cs.CL]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.13101>.
- [13] Yixuan Tang and Yi Yang. *MultiHop-RAG: Benchmarking Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Multi-Hop Queries*. 2024. arXiv: [2401 . 15391](https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.15391) [cs.CL]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.15391>.
- [14] Prof. Dr. Dominique Jakob University of Zurich. *Merkblatt zum Bundesgericht*. <https://www.ius.uzh.ch/dam/jcr:00000000-3807-9fc9-ffff-ffffe20f0b3b/MerkblattzumBundesgericht.pdf>. Accessed: 2025-08-19. 2013.
- [15] Wolfgang Portmann, Isabelle Wildhaber, and Roger Rudolph. *Schweizerisches Arbeitsrecht*. de. 2024.
- [16] Christoph Leuenberger and Beatrice Uffer-Tobler. *Schweizerisches Zivilprozessrecht*. de. 2nd ed. Stämpflis juristische Lehrbücher. Bern, Switzerland: Stämpfli Verlag, Nov. 2016.
- [17] Jolanta Kren Kostkiewicz. *Schuldbetreibungs- und Konkursrecht (PrintPlus)*. de. 2023.
- [18] Mark Pieth and Monika Simmler. *Strafrecht Besonderer Teil*. de. 2024.
- [19] Isabelle Wildhaber and Heinz Rey. *Ausservertragliches Haftpflichtrecht*. de. 2024.
- [20] Daniel Staehelin and Pascal Grolimund. *Zivilprozessrecht: Unter Einbezug des Anwaltsrechts und des internationalen Zivilprozessrechts*. de. 2024.